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Executive Summary of White Paper (5000 character limit)

Line Intensity Mapping (LIM) is a rapidly emerging technique which promises new insights into the evolution of the universe across cosmic history. By measuring the integrated emission of spectral lines over a broad range of frequencies one can observe the statistical properties of distant galaxies. LIM surveys have depth and resolution requirements that are greatly relaxed compared to direct- imaging surveys. A coordinated, comprehensive, multi-line intensity mapping effort can efficiently probe over 80% of the volume of the universe while retaining the redshift resolution necessary to make three-dimensional maps - a feat beyond the reach of other methods. Such measurements can uniquely address a wide range of pressing mysteries in galaxy evolution, cosmology, and fundamental physics. Among them are the history of star formation, the process of reionization, cosmological inflation, the validity of general relativity, and the nature of dark matter and dark energy.

Several LIM efforts are already well underway, a number of which with significant Canadian involvement. Surveys targeting the 21 cm line have been active for some time, including the Canadian-led CHIME experiment. Recently, experiments targeting other atomic and molecular lines across the electromagnetic spectrum have garnered significant interest as well. Such observations have useful synergies with each other, and are highly complementary to astrophysical measurements from other surveys that Canada is a key participant in.

With continued investment over the next decade, LIM experiments will have a transformative impact on our understanding of the distant universe. However, significant modeling, analysis, and interpretation challenges remain in these measurements. We therefore motivate a broad-based program of line intensity mapping theoretical, simulation, and observational efforts to ensure that intensity mapping techniques reach their full potential.

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1 Introduction

Line intensity mapping (LIM) is a novel method for exploring astrophysics and cosmology in the extragalactic universe. Traditional observations rely on the ability to directly image individual high-redshift galaxies, which imposes often onerous aperture, time, and spectroscopic requirements on large surveys. LIM surveys, by contrast, seek to map the large-scale intensity fluctuations of a chosen spectral line (see Kovetz et al., 2017, and references therein for a review). By targeting narrow line features, it is possible to create tomographic maps over large volumes with redshift resolution comparable to spectroscopic surveys. These maps are thus sensitive to all sources of line emission in a target volume, and thus enable the universal study of galaxy formation and evolution. As high angular resolution is not required, LIM can cover large sky areas in limited observing time, allowing various tests of the standard cosmological model and access to underexplored volumes of the universe.

To roughly demonstrate the potential of intensity maps for galaxy science, Figure 1 shows a toy simulation of a LIM observation of the CO(1-0) rotational transition with a current-generation single-dish observatory to a direct observation with the Very Large Array (VLA). A blind survey covering this simulated field would take ~ 4500 hours with the VLA, and would only detect $\sim 1\%$ of the CO emitters. The LIM survey, on the other hand, can make statistical measurements of the properties of all of the emitters with ~ 1500 hours of integration using a much cheaper observatory.

Figure 1: A simulated 2.5 deg^2 field with galaxy positions (left) and the corresponding CO intensity field (right). CO luminosities were simulated using a Schechter function model (Breysse et al., 2017). Sources bright enough to detect with 1 hour of VLA time are marked in red (see Li et al. 2016).

As far as large-scale structure measurements, consider that the precision of many cosmological measurements improves with the number N_{modes} of accessible modes. Cosmic microwave background (CMB) experiments, which probe a two-dimensional surface at redshift $z \sim 1100$, contain order 10^7 modes. Intensity maps may resemble CMB-type observations at first glance, but they carry two important advantages. First, there is no equivalent of the Silk damping effect which smooths out small-scale perturbations in the CMB. Second, the tomographic nature of intensity maps allows observations in three dimensions rather than two, with the total number of available modes in principle reaching as high as 10^{16} (Loeb & Zaldarriaga, 2004), though in practice this will be limited by sky coverage, foregrounds, and nonlinearities.

LIM is a young but rapidly developing field in which Canadian investment has and can continue to have a substantial impact. The first successful intensity mapping observations were led by a Canadian team (Chang et al., 2010a), consisting of measurements of the 21-cm spin-flip line in cross-correlation with galaxy surveys. Since then, a wide variety of LIM experiments have been developed, many with significant Canadian involvement (e.g., Masui et al., 2013; Keating et al., 2016; Switzer et al., 2013; Anderson et al., 2018; Pullen et al., 2018). These

experiments target a number of different spectral lines in addition to 21 cm, including CO rotational transitions, the CII fine-structure lines, other hydrogen lines such as $\text{Ly}\alpha$, $\text{H}\alpha$, $\text{H}\beta$, and a number of others. Targeting many lines maximizes potential science output as different lines trace different properties of high-redshift emitters. This also helps to minimize overall risk as the different systematics of different observations allow many opportunities for cross-correlations and verification. Because many of these experiments are modest in scale, there is room for large impact from Canadian contributions. Below we describe a number of current or proposed experiments in which we advocate new or continuing Canadian support.

In addition to the experimental landscape, there is need for significant investment in theory, analysis, and simulation tools for LIM observations. Examples of modelling efforts for various observable line transitions include Gong et al. (2012); Li et al. (2016); Mashian et al. (2015); Visbal & Loeb (2010); Breysse et al. (2015); Padmanabhan (2018, 2019); Bernal et al. (2019a); Chung et al. (2018) and Pullen et al. (2013). Intensity maps contain a large amount of useful information, but extracting and interpreting this information amid noise, foregrounds, RFI, and other systematics are challenging tasks. In addition, LIM measures baryonic tracers of dark matter and is affected by so-called ‘astrophysical systematic’ effects (illustrated for the case of HI in Padmanabhan et al., 2015, 2019) resulting from the fact that the astrophysics is poorly understood at these redshifts (a consideration that is much less severe for the CMB). There are, however, excellent prospects to identify and mitigate these effects, by combining information from independent astrophysical probes into a systematic framework (e.g., Padmanabhan et al., 2017; Padmanabhan & Refregier, 2017). There is already an active community in Canada working on these problems. We recommend continued investment along these lines via postdoctoral fellowships and dedicated theory funding.

In this white paper we advocate for continuing the current comprehensive, multi-frequency program of LIM observations made by small- and medium-scale experiments, with emphasis on cross-collaboration data sharing. We also recommend additional investment in modeling, theory, and simulation efforts.

2 Science Potential

LIM observations have the potential for transformative impacts across a wide variety of fields. Here we briefly summarize some of their most interesting applications.

2.1 Galaxy Evolution

LIM is uniquely suited to study several open questions in the field of galaxy formation and evolution. What is the history of cosmic star formation? How does the interstellar medium (ISM) evolve across cosmic time? How do galaxy properties depend on their environment, and how do they interact with their surrounding intergalactic medium (IGM)? How are the galaxies we see today shaped by feedback? With large spatial volumes, sensitivity to faint objects, and excellent redshift resolution, LIM data will provide a powerful complement to direct surveys, whether wide surveys like LSST or DESI, or deep observations with instruments like JWST.

By targeting many different lines, the effort we advocate for here can access multiple emission lines coming from different phases of the ISM and IGM. CO lines trace cold molecular clouds (Bolatto et al., 2013), while CII from these clouds and their surroundings provide a critical source of cooling (Dalgarno & McCray, 1972). Neutral hydrogen in various phases in and around galaxies can be seen in lines like $\text{Ly}\alpha$, $\text{H}\alpha$ and $\text{H}\beta$ (Villaescusa-Navarro et al., 2018; Silva et al., 2017; Pullen et al., 2014), while HII regions are traced by lines like OIII (which has been used to great effect in ultra-high-redshift ALMA spectroscopy, Moriwaki et al. 2018). Many of these lines scale strongly with star formation rate (see, e.g. Silva et al., 2017; Yue et al., 2015; Li et al., 2016), perhaps the most crucial factor in the broader galactic ecosystem. As LIM provides the integrated emission from every source in a volume, these surveys can yield a complete census of star formation-tracing gas, producing unparalleled measurements of the cosmic star formation history (Kistler et al., 2013; Breysse et al., 2016; Lagache, 2018).

As in the local universe, observations using multiple spectral lines are often much more powerful than the sum of their parts. LIM is no different. A multi-line effort like the one proposed here can gain significantly more utility through cross-correlations. Two LIM observations in combination allow measurements of how line luminosities vary with respect to one another, making it possible to dissect the ISM in greater detail (Serra et al., 2016; Breysse

& Rahman, 2017). One can also correlate intensity maps with galaxy surveys. In addition to being a powerful proof against foregrounds and systematics, this makes it possible to project out specific galaxy populations from confused intensity maps. For example, one could seek to explore how gas content depends on galaxy color (Wolz et al., 2017), or correlate with quasar maps to study AGN feedback (Breyse & Alexandroff, 2019).

2.2 Reionization

The Epoch of Reionization (EoR) was the last great phase transition in cosmological history, when the first stars, accreting black holes, and galaxies formed and their UV emission photoionized their surrounding neutral gas (Loeb & Furlanetto, 2013). Since this process appears at very high redshift, it remains relatively unexplored despite its importance. Key open questions include: When exactly did reionization occur, and how much of the IGM is ionized as a function of redshift? Is reionization driven by small numbers of bright objects or large numbers of faint sources, and is it sourced by star forming galaxies or accreting black holes? What is the topology of reionization, as ionized bubbles expand out from UV emitters? These questions tie deeply in to the nature of early structure formation and the first galaxies. By simultaneously mapping the evolution of gas both within and outside of galaxies LIM can provide unique insight into the EoR.

The 21 cm line by its very nature provides the most direct probe of the reionization process, as it primarily traces the neutral phase of the IGM as it disappears. The first detections of 21 cm fluctuations from the EoR are expected within the next few years (DeBoer et al., 2017), and Canadian expertise will be crucial in obtaining them. Our understanding can be further improved by surveys of other lines, such as CII, OIII, CO, and others which trace the galaxies which cause reionization. In conjunction, maps of the Ly α line probe recombinations both within the ISM and IGM (Gong et al., 2012; Lidz et al., 2011). Combining all of these data will shed new light on the interplay between the IGM and the ionizing sources.

2.3 Fundamental Cosmology

Led by CMB and galaxy survey observations, precision observational cosmology has measured the parameters of the standard cosmological model (Λ CDM) with percent-level precision. Several gaping holes remain in the theory, such as: what was responsible for the epoch of inflation at the beginning of cosmic history? What objects or particles make up dark matter? And what is the nature of Dark Energy? The potential of the CMB to constrain extensions to Λ CDM, including primordial non-Gaussianity and evolving dark energy, has been largely exhausted. Most galaxy redshift surveys have been restricted to $z \lesssim 1$, and therefore have only covered a small fraction of accessible linear modes. Intensity mapping, with its ability to quickly cover large volumes of the universe, is well-suited to harvest new information about these deep mysteries.

With their ability to tomographically map wide redshift ranges, LIM surveys can observe baryon acoustic oscillations continuously from low to high redshift, allowing them to test new models of cosmic evolution and evolving dark energy (Bandura et al., 2014; Bernal et al., 2019b). These measurements can shed new light on the tension between measurements of the Hubble constant (Riess et al., 2016; Planck Collaboration et al., 2018; Freedman et al., 2019) by bridging the distance gap between their sources. With their potential sensitivity to very large scales, LIM measurements can improve measurements of primordial non-Gaussianity, potentially approaching the coveted target of $f_{NL} \sim 1$ and beyond (Moradinezhad Dizgah et al., 2019; Fonseca et al., 2018). Many dark matter models produce signatures which can be seen in LIM surveys. LIM can improve the experimental sensitivity to dark matter models which radiatively decay or annihilate by \sim ten orders of magnitude (Creque-Sarbinowski & Kamionkowski, 2018). Measurements in the cosmic dawn era can provide new insights into warm dark matter and dark matter-baryon interactions (Sitwell et al., 2014; Carucci et al., 2015; Chatterjee et al., 2019). Through precision measurements of reionization as described above, LIM surveys can help measure the optical depth to reionization, a critical nuisance parameter for CMB observations (Liu et al., 2016). Gravitational lensing of these fluctuations can be leveraged to further improve our understanding of many of these topics (Foreman et al., 2018).

Figure 2: Various current, upcoming, and future LIM experiments. Those with Canadian involvement are highlighted in red.

2.4 Discovery Space

Beyond the target science cases of these experiments, LIM surveys collectively represent a large potential discovery space. There may exist previously unknown phenomena which can be detected by blindly mapping large areas of sky with high spectral resolution. Most notably, the Canadian Hydrogen Intensity Mapping Experiment (CHIME), which was designed with HI intensity mapping as its primary science case, has become by far the best experiment in the world for detecting and characterizing fast radio bursts (The CHIME/FRB Collaboration et al., 2019). Other experiments across the electromagnetic spectrum offer opportunities for similarly great discoveries.

3 Experimental Landscape

From the earliest stages, Canada has played a leading role in the landscape of intensity mapping experiments. Figure 2 outlines the range of experiments currently proposed, funded, in progress, or complete. Red boxes indicate experiments with Canadian involvement, indicating the broad Canadian leadership in this rapidly developing field.

3.1 GBT/Parkes

The line intensity mapping method was pioneered by the HI survey at $z=0.8$ using the Green Bank Telescope (Chang et al., 2010b; Masui et al., 2013; Switzer et al., 2013). The Canadian-led survey made the first detection of large-scale structure using intensity mapping by both cross-correlating with an optical galaxy catalogue. Used in tandem with upper limits from the autocorrelation (containing residual foreground contamination), the survey measured the large-scale clustering properties of neutral hydrogen. Since neutral hydrogen is fuel for star formation, this measurement informs our understanding of galaxy evolution and the role of feedback mechanisms on the rate at which gas is converted into stars. The survey has been extended to low redshift using the Parkes Telescope (Anderson et al., 2018), which was able to further characterize the hydrogen content of galaxy environments based on galaxy type. The GBT survey has demonstrated that foregrounds can be subtracted by four orders of magnitude in power, a figure that continues to improve with ongoing analysis.

3.2 CHIME

The Canadian Hydrogen Intensity Mapping Experiment (CHIME) is a purpose built, drift-scan, radio interferometer, located at the Dominion Radio Astrophysical Observatory in the interior of British Columbia¹. It consists of four cylindrical reflectors, with each 100m long north-south and 20m wide, populated by 1024 dual polarization antennas, observing between 400-800 MHz. With this design CHIME has an instantaneously large field of view (> 200 sq deg), and maps almost the whole sky observable from its latitude each day. CHIME has been operating since early 2018, with commissioning finishing in late 2018.

¹<https://chime-experiment.ca>

The primary purpose of CHIME is to map large-scale structure between $z = 0.8$ – 2.5 and make precision measurements of the Baryon Acoustic scale across this redshift range. This will enable sub-percent-level constraints on the expansion history allowing it to probe fundamental cosmology such as the nature of Dark Energy. Additionally, CHIME’s design means it is very effective general purpose survey instrument allowing additional backends like the very successful FRB search instrument (The CHIME/FRB Collaboration et al., 2019), pulsar timing instrument (Ng, 2018), and an upcoming 21cm absorption survey.

3.3 HERA

The Hydrogen Epoch of Reionization Array (HERA) is a low-frequency radio interferometer located in the South African Karoo desert. When construction is complete in 2020, it will consist of 350 dishes, each of which is 14 m in diameter (DeBoer et al., 2017). The dishes will be arranged in a hybrid configuration, with 320 of them arranged in a dense hexagonal core, while the remaining 30 serve as outriggers ~ 1 km away from the core (Dillon & Parsons, 2016). Broadband Vivaldi feeds suspended at the focal point of each feed enable HERA to observe the 21 cm line from $z \sim 6$ to 27. HERA is a drift-scan telescope with no moving parts, ensuring stability in the instrument.

HERA is designed to have sufficient sensitivity to make a high-significance measurement of the 21 cm power spectrum during reionization (~ 20 to 100σ , depending on assumptions about foreground contaminants; Pober et al. 2014). This will allow detailed constraints on the properties of first-generation galaxies, such as their mass function and their UV and X-ray luminosities, as well as properties of the high-redshift IGM, such as the statistical abundance of dense clumps of hydrogen (Kern et al., 2017). Additionally, HERA can place model-dependent constraints on the ionization history of our Universe (Liu & Parsons, 2016), potentially improving future CMB results that are affected by reionization (such as the sum of neutrino masses; Liu et al. 2016)

3.4 HIRAX

The Hydrogen Intensity and Real-time Analysis eXperiment (HIRAX, Newburgh et al., 2016) is an intensity mapping project to be built in the Karoo region of South Africa. HIRAX will be comprised of a compact interferometric array of 6m parabolic dishes, instrumented with dual polarisation feeds operating from 400–800 MHz. The primary science goals of HIRAX are to 1) constrain the equation of state of Dark Energy by mapping large scale structure at high redshift ($z = 0.8$ – 2.5), and 2) detect and study radio transients such as fast radio bursts and pulsars. To do so, HIRAX will conduct a survey of 15,000 square degrees of the southern sky, mapping the distribution of large scale structure through 21cm intensity mapping while simultaneously feeding data into dedicated backends for real-time transient searches. Currently the project is funded for a 256 element array with plans to extend up to 1024 dishes. First phase construction is expected to commence in 2020. Canada is playing a leading role in HIRAX, with particular focus on the dish/mount design and verification (NRC/McGill), the ADC/channelization F-engine (McGill) and the cross-correlation X-engine (Dunlap/Toronto). Canadian institutions, particularly McGill, Dunlap/CITA/Toronto, and UBC, will play major roles in pipeline development and data analysis and interpretation.

3.5 CCAT-prime

CCAT-prime is a 6-m extreme field-of-view telescope operating at $200\mu\text{m}$ to 3mm wavelength, anticipated to see first light in 2021 at 5600m altitude on Cerro Chajnantor in Chile. It will aid in understanding the processes of structure formation and probe the underlying dark matter density fluctuations by mapping the large-scale three-dimensional (3D) clustering of star-forming galaxies. This is done using wide-field spectroscopy of the aggregate [CII] $158\mu\text{m}$ signal from star formation regions in galaxies to perform 3D tomography of the spatial fluctuations due to large-scale structure at $z = 3.5$ - 8.0 , all the way from “cosmic noon” into the epoch of reionization.

The EoR-Spec module being built as part of the Prime Cam instrument will provide maps over several 8 deg^2 survey fields in [CII] emission across this redshift range in the first five years of its operations. It will simultaneously provide measurements of the [OIII] $88\mu\text{m}$ line from HII regions in $z > 7$ galaxies and of multiple CO lines at virtually any redshift. This data will be highly complementary to targeted studies of individual galaxies at the same redshifts with ALMA, ngVLA, JWST, and OST by providing information on the large-scale structure in which

those sources are embedded and the aggregate signal from sources too faint to be individually detected by those facilities. The CCAT-prime team includes a large contingent of Canadian researchers at several institutions.

The CCAT-prime team has been awarded 80% of the funding required for the complete project. The Canadian CCAT-prime partners are currently applying to CFI for the final 20% that is required beginning in 2021 for shipping, assembly, and commissioning of the telescope after fabrication is completed in Germany. These CFI funds will also be needed for construction of facilities in Chile, software, and to build the central module of prime-Cam – the main camera for CCAT-prime.

3.6 COMAP

The CO Mapping Array Pathfinder (COMAP) will open new windows on both the Epoch of Reionization (EoR) and the Epoch of Galaxy Assembly by using carbon monoxide (CO) lines to trace the evolution of star formation in galaxies through these two important epochs. COMAP Phase I comprises a 10.4-m telescope, located at the Owens Valley Radio Observatory (OVRO), equipped with a 19-pixel spectrometer array that will map a total of about 10 square degrees of sky in the frequency range 26-34 GHz, with spectral resolution of 2 MHz. In Phase I, COMAP is thus sensitive to CO(2-1) emission from the EoR and CO(1-0) emission from the epoch of galaxy assembly.

Phase I science operations have begun and the initial 2-year observing campaign is underway. These observations will allow constraints to be placed on the CO luminosity function and trace the cosmic molecular gas abundance and star formation history at $z=2.4-3.4$. The Canadian Institute for Theoretical Astrophysics is playing a leading role in modeling the CO signal from both epochs probed by the experiment, ensuring that the collaboration is ready to interpret the experimental data when they become available.

3.7 TIME

TIME, the Tomographic Ionized-Carbon Intensity Mapping Experiment is, a pathfinder instrument designed to measure the fine structure line, [CII], during the epoch of reionization and the CO molecular lines at the peak of star formation, $z \sim 1 - 2$. TIME is a grating spectrometer backed with Transition Edge Sensor (TES) bolometers sensitive in the 200-300 GHz band. The instrument has been deployed for an engineering run on a 12 m ALMA prototype antenna on Kitt Peak and will observe for 3 seasons starting in 2020. Canadian involvement with TIME will be growing as PI Crites will be joining the University of Toronto and the Dunlap Institute.

3.8 EXCLAIM

EXCLAIM, the EXperiment for Cryogenic Large-Aperture Intensity Mapping, is a balloon-borne instrument that will map the CII fine-structure line for redshifts $2.5 < z < 3.5$ and various CO molecular lines at redshifts $z < 1$. The survey will comprise 400 deg² in the southern hemisphere using a cryogenically-cooled spectrometer over the spectral range 410-520 GHz. These measurements will be used to trace star formation and constrain models of the interstellar medium. EXCLAIM will observe over 3 annual 10-hour flights starting in 2021.

4 Recommendations for the next decade

- **Continue experimental support-** Canada has played a large role in the instrumental projects in LIM especially probes of 21 cm signals, e.g. CHIME. They have also played a role in pathfinder instrument probing lines that will be used to probe cosmology and astrophysics over different epoch in the history of the universe. To continue to be a leader in this emerging field especially as the field expands to the use of these cutting edge probes including [CII] and CO, investment in future instrumentation, including telescope platforms and detector development will be critical.
- **Encourage theoretical efforts-** Realizing the raw potential of LIM data will require substantial modeling, simulation, and analysis efforts. These are highly complex data sets, and care must be taken both to ensure that we are actually seeing the cosmological signal clean of foregrounds and systematics and to connect

measured luminosity fluctuations to underlying physics. We also recommend embedding theorists in experimental collaborations to ensure that each experiment can make the most use of its unique measurements.

- **Maximize cross-correlation opportunities-** Cross-correlations, both between intensity maps of different lines and between intensity maps and other cosmological observables provide a critical means of ensuring signal veracity. Also, as described above, they can dramatically improve our ability to learn about galaxies. It is therefore important to encourage coordination and data sharing as much as possible between different collaborations.

1: How does the proposed initiative result in fundamental or transformational advances in our understanding of the Universe?

A LIM survey provides a statistical measurement of the entire population of line emitting objects over cosmological volumes with redshift accuracy comparable to spectroscopic galaxy surveys. The distribution of line intensities enables novel probes of ISM/IGM physics, particularly in faint populations which are difficult to observe directly. In particular, LIM enables tracing the evolution of both the neutral IGM and the earliest star-forming galaxies during the Epoch of Reionization. Finally, the resulting tomographic, large-volume maps provide access to many large-scale-structure modes enable high-precision constraints on fundamental cosmology.

2: What are the main scientific risks and how will they be mitigated?

The primary scientific risks of LIM surveys are foreground contamination and astrophysical interpretation. Maps of line emission also include contributions from Milky Way and other astrophysical foregrounds in addition to the cosmological signal, which must be carefully removed. Even given clean maps, it is challenging to relate confused maps of line emitters to underlying galactic and cosmological physics given the complex processes that give rise to line emission.

Both of these risks can be mitigated by the broad-based program of experiments we recommend here. Different lines and telescope designs suffer from different foregrounds and systematics, motivating the use of several moderately-priced experiments. Cross-correlations can further reduce the risk of unsubtracted contamination. Different lines are also sensitive to different astrophysical processes, so using multiple lines dramatically aids in interpretation, especially when cross-correlations are included. We also stress the need to fund theory, simulation, and analysis efforts to combat these risks.

3: Is there the expectation of and capacity for Canadian scientific, technical or strategic leadership?

Canada has been a leader in the LIM field since its inception, and in fact the first detection of a LIM signal was made by Canadian astronomers. Canada plays a significant leadership role in several proposed and currently operating experiments. The relatively small size of many of these collaborations presents the opportunity for large contributions from modest investment. Finally, the theory community in Canada has made and continues to make key contributions to modeling, simulation, and theory efforts.

4: Is there support from, involvement from, and coordination within the relevant Canadian community and more broadly?

As stated above, the Canadian community is already heavily involved in several of these experiments, and support for these techniques in the broader cosmological community has grown significantly in the past decade. One key recommendation of this white paper is to pursue stronger coordination and data sharing between

different experiments, and between the experimental and theoretical communities to maximize the science output in the next decade and beyond.

5: Will this program position Canadian astronomy for future opportunities and returns in 2020-2030 or beyond 2030?

With several early-generation experiments currently under construction or in progress we expect significant science returns in the next 5-10 years, including the first LIM autocorrelation detections. Lessons learned from these first generation surveys will position the Canadian community to play an important role in future observations from 2030 onwards. In addition, maps generated from LIM experiments represent a powerful legacy data set which can be combined with future data to generate further insights into the high redshift universe. Finally, Canadian involvement in LIM surveys positions the community to take advantage of the large discovery space offered by these observations, demonstrated most notably by the success of the CHIME experiment as an instrument for fast radio burst detection.

6: In what ways is the cost-benefit ratio, including existing investments and future operating costs, favourable?

Significant investments have been made already, as several experiments discussed here are already funded or in progress (see Fig. 2). Intensity mapping experiments also tend to compare favorably in terms of cost to direct-imaging surveys. CHIME is expected to produce cosmological results of a similar quality to the DESI spectroscopic survey, but at a cost roughly ~ 5 times less.

7: What are the main programmatic risks and how will they be mitigated?

Several experiments have not yet obtained full funding, necessitating continued work to ensure they go forward as planned. However, enough surveys have been funded to ensure significant scientific output. Given the relatively novel nature of the intensity mapping observable, there may be unforeseen analysis challenges that will delay the release of results. This can be mitigated by ensuring sufficient resources are given to modeling and analysis efforts in addition to the observations themselves.

8: Does the proposed initiative offer specific tangible benefits to Canadians, including but not limited to interdisciplinary research, industry opportunities, HQP training, EDI, outreach or education?

The unique hardware requirements of intensity mapping experiments offer the opportunity for strong industry connections, for example in the construction of powerful correlators for large interferometers. In addition, unlike programs where researchers apply for time on specific telescopes, the wide variety of smaller experiments proposed here offer the chance to train large numbers of students in hardware work. Fewer and fewer opportunities of this nature exist in astronomy as time passes. The large data sets produced by these experiments constitute a substantial big-data challenge, motivating interdisciplinary overlap with the computer sciences.

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